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Salary and Fringe Benefits as Correlates of Attrition among Public Primary School Teachers in Borno State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study was a comparative analysis between salary and fringe benefits on attrition among public primary school teachers in Borno State, Nigeria. The study determined relationship between salary, and fringe benefits and teacher attrition. Based on the objectives; to determine the relationship between salary and teacher turnover in public primary schools, Borno State, Nigeria and to determine the relationship between fringe benefits and teacher turnover in public primary schools, Borno State, Nigeria the research tested null hypotheses on the relationship between salary and teacher attrition and the relationship between fringe benefits and teacher attrition at 0.05 level of significance. The study used correlation research design. The population of the study were 18,758 teachers and a sample of 1, 876 teachers during the 2023/2024 academic session were randomly selected. The researchers used questionnaire and proforma for data collection. The data collected were analyzed and Hypotheses were tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC). The findings of the study revealed that there is significant relationship between salary and teacher attrition and fringe benefits and teacher attrition. Based on the findings, the researchers recommend that Borno State Government should make improvements on the salary of teachers as the study showed that teachers were not satisfied with the monthly salary, they receive which led to teacher attrition and Borno State Government should make improvements on the fringe benefits enjoyed by teachers as the study showed that teachers were not satisfied with the fringe benefits, they enjoy which led to teacher attrition among others.

Keywords: Personnel Remuneration, Teacher Attrition, public primary Schools

Introduction

Education has remained as an instrument of change and national development. Thus, the National Policy on Education (2013) states that the Federal Government of Nigeria has adopted education as an instrument per excellence for effecting national development. Teachers are the ones to carry out this vital task of meeting Nigeria's target of E.F.A. Adamu (2010) stressed that no nation develops without education and education is not possible without teachers because teachers inculcate what is worthwhile to learners who in turn utilize the knowledge, skills, values, and attitudes to develop the nation. However, teachers who are saddled with this responsibility of effecting national change in the nation's economic manpower development for global deliberation on Education for All (E.F.A) are exiting the teaching profession in large numbers especially in the Nigerian schools, primary schools in Borno State inclusive. Nel and Werner (2009) defined personnel attrition as the movement of employee in and out of the bondage of the organization. The rate of teacher attrition has become an issue of concern to both policy makers, educational planners and administrators which attracted series of researches in both developing and developed nations of the world. In Nigeria, the rate of teacher attrition varies within geo-political zones (Wushishi, Foori, Basra & Baki, 2013). Staff turnover can be perceived as a final or permanent act. Remuneration has great influence on teacher attrition all over the world Assefa (2011), Egu, Nwuju and Chionye (2011) and Wushishi Foori, Basri and Baki (2013). The remuneration structure of any organization which ensures congruence

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between employee and organizational goals is sure of reducing cases of attrition, Ghana National Association of Teachers (GNAT, 2010).

Nwapa (2019) conducted a study that determined the causes and consequences of male teachers' attrition in primary and secondary schools in Ebonyi State, Nigeria and the result of the study revealed that low level of salary and poor working condition contributed to male teachers' attrition. Cyril, Ugwuada and Bello (2015) examined the causes of science and technical teachers' attrition and strategies for retention in Adamawa State secondary schools. The findings of Cyril, Ugwuada and Bello (2015) revealed that poor condition of service, poor salary and wages contributed to teacher attrition. Ekabu (2019) conducted research on the relationship between the level of remuneration and turnover intentions of public secondary school teachers in Meru County. The findings showed that remuneration has a negative and an inverse relationship with turnover intention. Caluza (2019) determined the impact of job satisfaction on teacher turnover in independent Christian schools in Johannesburg, South Africa which showed that there was no significant relationship between salary and attrition. Onesmus, Waita, Beth and Julius (2016) conducted a study on factors influencing teacher attrition in public secondary schools in Mbooni East Sub-County. The findings of their study revealed that perpetual teacher attrition was due to poor salaries among other factors. Nguyen (2020) conducted a study on teacher attrition and retention in Kansas. The findings revealed that teachers' salary may influence teachers' decision to stay or leave. Sribayak, Tangkiengsirisin and Hongboontri (2018) conducted a study on factors influencing teacher attrition in Thai context and salary was believed to be among the reasons why EFL teachers leave or consider leaving their teaching career. Assefa, (2011) conducted research to determine factors that cause teachers' turnover in government and private secondary schools in Addis Ababa city administration in a comparative manner and the findings showed that inadequate salary that teachers get was among other factors that aggravate the turnover of teachers both in government and private schools.

Salisu (2020) conducted a study on the influence of post- primary school teachers' job satisfaction and empowerment on teacher turnover intention in Katsina State, Nigeria and revealed that teachers' professional development is one of the things that influences teacher turnover intentions. Madumere, Ukala and Akachuku (2018) determined the management of teacher attrition rate for quality education delivery in public secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. The study concluded that better services and good welfare packages in terms of fringe benefits for teachers can reduce teacher attrition rate. Paying attention to teachers by giving equal regards with other professions will increase teachers' retention. Hardianto, Rugaiyah and Rosyidi (2019) conducted a study to see the effect of reward and job satisfaction on teachers' turnover intentions and showed that there is significant relationship between fringe benefit and teacher attrition. Okeke, Okoforcha and Ekwesianya (2019) examined the causes of teacher attrition and strategies for teacher retention in secondary schools in Anambra State and the findings of the study showed that teacher attrition takes place for a number of reasons which included low social recognition for teachers and lack of opportunities for professional development. Kyalo, James and Kimencu (2018) carried out a study which determined how human resource management practices predict tutor turnover intentions in primary teacher training colleges (PTTCs) in Kenya and found that training, career development and performance management were poorly practiced and that they significantly and negatively predict tutor turnover intentions. Okey (2020) examined job satisfaction and teacher turnover in the management of secondary education in Calabar Municipal Local Government Area, Cross River State, Nigeria and the findings revealed that a relationship exists between job satisfaction and teacher turnover.

Agboola and Offong (2018) examined the relationship between occupational incentives and teacher retention in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria and revealed that significant relationship existed between job security, remuneration, promotion, welfare and teacher retention in private secondary schools. Mugo (2018) conducted a study on factors contributing to labour turnover among public secondary school teachers in Kenya and identified the factors that contributed to high turnover were recognition and involvement during decision making, lack of time for self-development, lack of an effective reward system, lack of further professional development for teachers or in-service trainings. Kyara (2013) determined how job satisfaction affects teachers' performance in primary schools in Tanzania. The study revealed that there was a very low level of satisfaction among teachers in terms of school supervision, communication feedback, availability of teaching and learning materials, school-parents' relationship, on the job training, teachers' promotion system (bar system), leave payment for teachers and the availability of public transport facilities.

Objectives of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to compare analysis between salary and fringe benefits on attrition among public primary school teachers in Borno State, Nigeria.

The specific objectives of the study were to determine;

- 1 relationship between salary and teacher attrition in public primary schools, Borno State, Nigeria.
- 2 relationships between fringe benefits and teacher attrition in public primary schools, Borno State, Nigeria.

Research Hypotheses

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The following research hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between salary and teacher attrition in public primary schools, Borno State, Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between fringe benefits and teacher attrition in public primary schools, Borno State, Nigeria.

Methodology

This study was a correlational research design which determined the relationship between personnel remuneration and teacher attrition in Borno State public primary schools, Nigeria over a period of five years (2016-2020). The design was correctional because it measured relationship between personnel remuneration and teacher attrition. Correlation provides an estimate of the strength of association between variables or the extent to which one variable is correlated with another (Brown & Dawling, 1998). The population for this study were all public primary school teachers in Borno State. As at the end of October, 2020, there were three hundred and forty-seven (347) primary schools with a total of eighteen thousand, seven hundred and fifty-eight (18,758) teachers (Borno State Universal Basic Education Board, 2021). The researchers considered ten percent (10%) of the teachers and twenty percent (20%) of the schools as sample of the population. The sample size for this study was one thousand eight hundred and seventy-six (1,876) teachers of the seventy (70) schools that were selected for the study. Two research instruments were used to obtain data for the study. The instruments used in this study were a set of questionnaires and a set of proforma. A self-designed inventory questionnaire on personnel remuneration and attrition of primary school teachers in Borno State was used for this study. The questionnaire consists of two sections, that is, Sections A and B. Section A sought for information on the demographic characteristics of the respondents such as name of the school, gender, age, qualification and length of service. Section B consists of 30 items that elicited for information on personnel remuneration. The proforma was used to record information on teacher attrition from official records. The data collected for the study were recorded and reduced to units for statistical analysis. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) was used to test hypotheses. Two variables are said to be correlated when an increase in one variable is regularly accompanied by an increase or decrease in the other (Brown & Dawling, 1998)

Presentation of Results

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between salary and teacher attrition in Borno State Public Primary Schools. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to determine the extent of relationship between salary and teacher attrition in Borno State public primary schools and the summary of the analysis is presented in the table below:

Table 1 Summary of the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient on the relationship between salary and teacher attrition in Borno State Public Primary Schools

Variable	N	Mean	SD	df	R	p-value	Remark
Salary	69	2.97	0.94	67	-0.639	0.00	Reject H ₀₂
Teacher Attrition	69	7.12	4.70				

The finding revealed that there is significant relationship between salary and teacher attrition with Pearson Product Moment Correlation $r = -0.639$. The table also revealed that the relationship between salary and teacher attrition is statistically significant because the p-value (0.00) is less than the level of significance (0.05). Therefore, hypothesis one was rejected and hence salary is a determinant of teacher attrition.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between fringe benefits and teacher attrition in Borno State public primary schools. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to determine the extent of relationship between fringe benefits and teacher attrition in Borno State public primary schools and the summary of the analysis is presented in the table below:

Table 4 Summary of the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient on the relationship between fringe benefits and teacher attrition in Borno State Public Primary Schools

Variable	N	Mean	SD	df	R	p-value	Remark
Fringe Benefit	69	3.22	0.85	67	-0.564	0.00	Reject H ₀₄
Teacher Attrition	69	7.12	4.70				

The finding revealed that there is significant relationship between fringe benefits and teacher attrition with Pearson Product Moment Correlation $r = -0.564$. The table also revealed that the relationship between fringe benefits and teacher attrition

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is statistically significant because the p-value (0,00) is less than the level of significance (0,05). Therefore, hypothesis two was rejected and hence fringe benefits has significant influence on teacher attrition.

Summary of Findings

The following were the main findings of the study:

1. There is significant relationship between salary and teacher attrition in public primary schools, Borno State, Nigeria.
2. There is significant relationship between fringe benefits and teacher attrition in public primary schools, Borno State, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study with respect to the relationship between salary and teacher attrition in public primary schools in Borno State, found that salary is significantly related to teacher attrition and had significant influence on teacher attrition. This finding is supported by the findings of Wushishi, Fooki, Basra and Baki (2013) which equally revealed that salary has great influence on teacher attrition in Niger state, Nigeria. Nwapa (2019) reported that salary and poor working condition contributed to the male teacher attrition in secondary schools in Ebonyi State, Nigeria. Wondimneh (2017) reported that the most significant condition for intentions of teacher turnover were lack of interest in the teaching profession and dissatisfaction with their current salary. However, this finding disagreed with that of Caluza (2019) which indicated that teachers did not intend to leave their jobs despite dissatisfaction with their salary. With regard to the findings on the relationship between fringe benefits and teacher attrition in public primary schools in Borno State, the study found a significant relationship between fringe benefits and teacher attrition. This finding is supported by Salisu (2020) who reported that lack of professional development is one of the things that influenced teacher turnover in post primary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria. This finding also agreed with that of Madumere, Ukala and Akachuku (2018) who reported that better services and good welfare packages in terms of fringe benefits for teachers can reduce teacher turnover rate. The finding of this study also concurred with that of Hardianto, Rugaiyah and Rosyidi (2019) which revealed that there is direct negative effect of rewards especially non-monetary rewards on turnover intentions. The finding of this study in terms of the relationship between fringe benefits and teacher attrition equally agreed with that of Bentil, Acquah and Akyiaw (2019) who found that teacher retention strategies such as improved salary, remuneration, provision of housing scheme, regular in-service training for teachers and scholarships for further studies to be likely boost their retention and reduce attrition.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that there was significant influence of salary and fringe benefits on teacher attrition in public primary schools in Borno State, Nigeria. It is concluded that lack reasonable salary and reasonable fringe benefits influenced teacher attrition in the public primary schools in Borno State, Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. The Borno State government should make improvement on the salary of teachers as the study showed the teachers were not satisfied with the amount they receive as salary which led to teacher attrition.
2. The Borno State Government should ensure that teachers enjoy benefits such as in-service training, payment of teachers' medical bills and provision of accommodation as the study revealed that teachers do not enjoy payment of medical bills or accommodation by the government and in-service training are not easily enjoyed by teachers which equally caused teacher turnover.

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